

STORAGE STABILITY OF GREEN BANANA FLOUR INCORPORATED RESISTANT STARCH RICH FUNCTIONAL MACARONI

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ABSTRACT

Pasta is a major source of carbohydrates; it has been associated with an increased risk of chronic illnesses like diabetes, obesity, and cardiovascular disease. In order to develop macaroni, unripe banana flour was incorporated at the level of 25, 35, 45, and 55%. The developed unripe banana flour incorporated macaroni were organoleptically evaluated for all sensory attributes. Among the four levels of incorporation, 45 per cent unripe banana flour incorporated macaroni was found to be the best in all organoleptic qualities compared to the other samples. The ideal cooking time for the developed macaroni was 8.30 to 6.67 minutes, the rehydration ratio was 1.82 to 2.19, the water absorption was 182.40 to 201.80 ml and the gruel loss was 3.62 to 5.69 per cent. The optimal concentration of resistant starch was 2.29 to 22.38 per cent. Among two packaging materials used for storing the macaroni samples compared to high-density polyethylene (HDPE), the macaroni packed in metalized polypropylene (MPP) had better cooking characteristics during storage.

KEYWORDS: Resistant starch, pasta products, macaroni, green banana, storage stability

INTRODUCTION

Although pasta was first attempted to be introduced in Italy in the 13th century, high-quality ingredients and efficient technology were not widely available until the 20th century. Nowadays, the majority of macaroni is produced using uninterpreted, greater capacity injection moulded pieces that combine extrusion and kneading in a single run, known as auger extrusion. The process of making pasta includes processing noodles, spaghetti, dried macaroni, and other ingredients (Walsh and colleagues, 1997). Unhealthy lifestyle choices are a major contributor to the emergence of a large number of illnesses. Due to its high glycaemic index, pasta has traditionally been viewed as a significant wheat product utilised as the main source of carbohydrates, raising blood sugar levels. This has a major impact on the chance of getting chronic diseases such as cancer, obesity, diabetes, heart disease, and other disorders (Tangthanantorn et al., 2021).

A healthy gastrointestinal tract is crucial for determining one's quality of life in today's fast-paced society, when food patterns are changing and lifestyle habits are disorganised (Ritthiruangdej et al., 2011). Pasta products are inexpensive, easy to prepare, and taste great, making them a vital component of human nutrition. They are easy to prepare, store, and maintain. They also greatly improve the nutritional quality of a meal by substituting cereals, pulses, bananas, and other foods high in resistant starch for some or all of the wheat flour (Flores-Silva *et al.*, 2015).

Owing to the rising demand for this product, further research is required to improve quality (Takacs et al., 2008). The study's findings indicate that when pasta is digested, sugars are progressively released, increasing postprandial blood glucose levels and the insulin response. According to Agama-Acevedo et al. (2009), pasta has a low glycaemic index (0 to 55) and a medium glycaemic index (56 to 69) when compared to bread. (Agama-Acevedo *et al.*, 2009). Owing to the rising demand for this product, further research is required to improve quality (Takacs et al., 2008). The study's findings indicate that when pasta is digested, sugars are progressively released, increasing postprandial blood glucose levels and the insulin response. According to Agama-Acevedo et al. (2009), pasta has a low glycaemic index (0 to 55) and a medium glycaemic index (56 to 69) when compared to bread.

Banana flour contains 6.3–15.5g/100g of fibre and 61.3–76.5g of starch per 100g of unripe bananas, according to Tribess et al. (2009). Vitamins A, C, E, and K, as well as minerals including calcium, phosphorus, and potassium, are abundant in banana flour (Biernacka et al., 2020). The flavour, scent, and appearance of banana flour are all unique. It also functions well with water. When heated, it expands and becomes translucent; when

frozen, it gelatinizes. Additionally, banana flour has the ability to cook due to its high amylose content (Oupathumpanont and Wisansakkul, 2021). Unripe bananas contain resistant starch, a type of starch that is fermented by bacteria in the large intestine rather than being broken down in the small intestine to produce short chain fatty acids and other organic acids. Resistant starch does not cause the body to create glucose and is linked to a reduced glycaemic index of carbs. Diabetes control and weight are associated with a lower glycaemic index (Tangthanantorn et al., 2021).

Customers are unlikely to eat enough vegetables and other foods high in fibre on their own, therefore adding unripe banana flour to pasta can help them get the nutritional benefits and it has some antioxidant qualities (Agama-Acevedo et al., 2009). Banana flour can be made from cooked or uncooked bananas. A lot of goods, including baby food, macaroni, bread, and pancakes, have been created by adding banana flour. Unripe bananas are rich in valuable nutrients called bioactive compounds and carbs. According to Ritthiruangdej et al. (2011), unripe banana flour has a low rate of enzymatic hydrolysis of carbohydrates and may be useful for broadening the range of low-glycaemic index meals offered to consumers. The aim of the study is to study about the storage behaviour of green banana flour incorporated resistant starch rich functional macaroni

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Non-perishable products

Whole wheat flour, salt, gingelly oil, pepper, cumin, turmeric, and chilli powders were purchased from a nearby Departmental store at Madurai. Food-grade Xanthan gum was purchased from Jan Enterprises, Chennai and was utilised as an additive to retain the extruded macaroni's rheological and textural qualities by replacing gluten.

Perishable products

Unripe banana bunches (*Musa acuminata*) was purchased from the Wholesale Banana Market in Madurai. The other ingredients such as onion, tomato, green chillies, capsicum, carrot, beans, cabbage, and coriander leaves were bought from Madurai's main vegetable market on the day of preparation of macaroni.

Materials for packaging

High Density Polyethylene (HDPE) bags and Metallized Polypropylene (MPP) were bought from Ramani Packaging (whole sale packaging store) at Madurai for keeping the macaroni samples for storage study.

Processing of flour from unripe bananas

Banana bunches were thoroughly inspected for no physical damage and colour was uniform with no black areas and lower-quality bananas were discarded. After selecting the best bananas, the skins were manually removed using a stainless steel knife. The chosen bananas were peeled, sliced into 4 mm thick pieces for rapid drying, and then treated for 10 minutes with a solution containing 0.1 per cent citric acid, 0.05 per cent potassium metabisulphite (K₂S₂O₅), and water (1:3) to prevent enzymatic browning (Kumar et al., 2019). After being dehydrated, the slices were ground for 120 seconds in a commercial pulverizer and sieved through 60 mesh sieves. Then the banana flour was collected, packed and stored in 250 g HDPE bags at room temperature for further investigation.

Development of unripe banana flour incorporated macaroni

Whole wheat flour, water and salt were the main ingredients in the Control macaroni (T₁). After weighing the flour blends (whole wheat flour 55%, unripe banana flour 45%), xanthan gum (1%), and salt (2%), the mixture was well mixed together to create unripe banana flour substituted macaroni (T₂). To ensure adequate mixing, the flour combinations were sifted three times before being sieved and kneaded with the required amount of water. The flour combinations were fed into the barrel of the extruder and kneaded for 30 minutes to ensure moisture was dispersed equally by the extruder shaft.

After fixing the appropriate brass die, the macaroni were extruded and the extruded macaroni was steam-cooked for fifteen minutes. After steaming, the macaroni was chilled and dried in a cabinet dryer at 60°C for four hours. The produced macaroni samples were packed in 200 gauge High Density Polyethylene (HDPE) bags and 200 gauge Metalized Polypropylene (MPP) bags to ensure the extruded macaroni remained safe and of high quality during storage. Over the period of 90 days of storage, the resistant starch content and storage stability of macaroni were analysed both before and after storage at 30 days of intervals. Hundal *et al.*, (2007) analysed the cooking parameters (cooking time, solid loss, cooked volume, and rehydration ratio) of the developed macaroni once in every thirty days during the storage period. Five grams of macaroni (18.5 cm in length, 1.4 cm in diameter, and 100 ml capacity) was put in a boiling test tube, half-filled with water, and submerged in a boiling water bath.

Cooking time

As soon as the water inside the test tube started to boil, the cooking time was noted. A little sample of the product was taken and squeezed between two glass slides for every 30 seconds to check for the existence of a white core, which indicates that the product is

undercooked. The product was subsequently heated until the white core was no longer visible between the two glass slides.

Gruel loss

Weighing was done regularly (every hour) until consistent results were obtained. The drained water was dried in a hot air oven at 110 °C. The amount of cooking loss or solid loss in macaroni was calculated by weighing the residue.

Resistant starch content

The resistant starch content of pasta products was determined using the McCleary and Monaghan (2002) method, and the results were reported accordingly.

Water Absorption

After cooking the products excess water was drained out, the amount of water that remained in the sample was measured and noted as water absorbed. The result on water absorption was expressed in millilitres per 100 grams of dry matter in the sample.

Rehydration of ratio

With a few minor adjustments, Kumar (2013) method was used to investigate the rehydration properties of macaroni products. The sample was first immersed in hot water (100°C) for a variety of durations, and their rehydration characteristics were examined for each period in order to determine the best time for rehydration. Every sample was monitored for 3,5,7,10,12 and 15 minutes and was noted that it took for the macaroni to rehydrate to the right texture was recorded. The results of the rehydration ratio were described as given below.

$$\text{Rehydration ratio} = \frac{\text{Drained weight of the rehydrated macaroni}}{\text{Weight of the dehydrated macaroni}}$$

Statistical analysis

As recommended by Gomez and Gomez (1984), statistical analysis was performed on the gathered data. A Factorial Completely Randomised Design (FCRD) design was used to evaluate the data from three replications in order to determine the effects of the storage time and packing materials on the cooked macaroni.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Changes in the cooking time (min) of the macaroni during storage

Table .1 shows the Changes in the cooking time (min) of the macaroni during storage. The macaroni in the control (T₁) took 8.3 minutes to cook. The cooking time during storage was shown to decrease gradually over a period of thirty to ninety days. A little difference was noted between the packing materials P₁ and P₂. It was observed that the cooking times for the control macaroni packed in P₁ and P₂ were reduced from 8.30 minutes to 8.20 minutes and 8.25, 8.13, 8.28, 8.02, and 8.11 minutes for control macaroni packed in P1 and P2 respectively. Similarly, after 30, 60, and 90 days of storage, the original cooking time of unripe banana flour-incorporated macaroni was reduced to 7.35 and 7.45, 7.11 and 7.34, and 6.57 and 7.22, respectively.

Table 1. Changes in the cooking time (min) of macaroni during storage

Storage days	T ₁		T ₂		T ₃		T ₄	
	P ₁	P ₂						
Initial	8.30	8.30	7.55	7.55	8.20	8.20	7.54	7.54
30	8.20	8.25	7.34	7.45	7.58	7.08	7.33	7.44
60	8.13	8.28	7.11	7.34	7.46	7.54	7.10	7.33
90	8.02	8.11	6.57	7.22	7.34	7.42	6.56	7.21
Factors			C.D.			SE(d)		
A			0.015			0.007		
B			0.010			0.005		
A X B			0.021			0.010		
C			0.015			0.007		
A X C			0.029			0.015		
B X C			0.021			0.010		
A X B X C			0.041			0.021		

Treatment details

T₁ : Wheat flour

T₂ : Wheat flour 60g + Unripe Banana flour 50g+ Xanthan gum 2g

Cooking times can be shortened by using unripe banana flour, which weakens and dilutes the protein network in the composite mix and allows for increased moisture absorption and heat transfer. (Rayas - Duarte *et al.*, 1996). Anggraeni *et al.*, (2018) reported that there was a decrease in cooking time as the amount of banana flour increased from 4 minutes to 2 minutes for noodles made with unripe banana flour in the range of 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50%. The decrease in cooking time when increasing the banana flour concentration in previous studies ranged from 8.6 , 5.1, and 4 minutes respectively for spaghetti cooked with 15%, 30%, and 45% unripe banana flour in composite mix (Osorio-Daz *et al.*, 2014).

Changes in the gruel loss (%) of Macaroni during storage

Table.2. Changes in the gruel loss (%) of macaroni during storage

Storage days	T ₁		T ₂		T ₃		T ₄	
	P ₁	P ₂						
Initial	3.62	3.62	5.33	5.33	5.52	5.52	5.35	5.35
30	3.73	3.67	5.44	5.39	5.63	5.57	5.46	5.41
60	3.86	3.73	5.56	5.46	5.76	5.64	5.56	5.47
90	3.96	3.80	5.69	5.53	5.88	5.72	5.68	5.55
Factors			C.D.			SE(d)		
A			0.007			0.003		
B			0.005			0.002		
A X B			0.009			0.005		
C			0.007			0.003		
A X C			0.013			0.007		
B X C			0.009			0.005		
A X B X C			0.018			0.009		

Treatment details

T₁ : Wheat flour

T₂ : Wheat flour 60g + Unripe Banana flour 50g+ Xanthan gum 2g

The changes in gruel loss (%) of macaroni during storage are given in Table 2. On the first day of storage, the macaroni had a gruel loss of 3.62% in T₁ and 5.33% in T₂. Every 30

days up to 90 days, the variations in the gruel loss of the macaroni were also examined for the Control (T_1) and uncooked banana flour incorporated Macaroni (T_2). For T_1 packed in P_1 , the initial and ultimate gruel loss was 3.62 and 3.96%, while for the sample packed in P_2 was 3.62 and 3.80%. Similarly, the banana flour incorporated macaroni (T_2), the initial gruel loss of 5.33 was found to have increased to 5.69 and 5.33 packed in P_1 and P_2 . The overall structure of the noodles will deteriorate as the amylose binding gluten network weakens, enabling solids to leach from the noodles during cooking, which is correlated with the increase in cooking loss when banana flour was added (Rayas-Duarte et al., 1996). Good quality pasta should have a solid loss of not more than 8%. (Gull and *et.al.*, 2015).

Nevertheless, in the present investigation the solid loss remained safe level and did not exceed 6%. A similar finding of increased cooking loss from 8.71 to 11.49 per cent was found while increasing banana flour (gluten), due to the relationship of nonglutenous components with wheat protein (Ritthiruangdej *et al.* 2011). According to Hernandez-Nava *et al.*,(2009) the high amylose concentration of unripe banana flour causes it to solubilize from the pasta surface during cooking, which increased solid loss.

Changes in the water absorption (ml/100g) of macaroni during storage:

Table 3 showed the variations in macaroni's water absorption throughout storage. The water absorption of raw macaroni with banana incorporation (T_2) and Control (T_1) varied by 182.40 and 195.15 millilitres, respectively. Over the storage period, both T_1 and T_2 showed a small increase in their capacity to absorb water. At the end of the 90-day storage period, the water absorption capacity of the control (T_1) macaroni packed in P_1 and P_2 was 187.90 ml and 185.88 ml, respectively. After 90 days of storage, it was also found that the amount of raw banana flour-incorporated macaroni (T_2) increased from 195.15 ml to 201.8 and 199.25 ml packed in P_1 and P_2 .

Table.3. Changes in the water absorption (ml/100g) of macaroni during storage

Storage days	T ₁		T ₂		T ₃		T ₄	
	P ₁	P ₂						
Initial	182.40	182.40	195.15	195.15	190.60	190.60	195.22	195.22
30	184.23	183.10	197.20	196.15	192.50	191.60	197.55	196.47
60	186.35	184.55	199.11	198.05	194.70	192.55	199.09	197.83
90	187.90	185.88	201.80	199.25	196.25	194.10	201.65	199.27
Factors			C.D.			SE(d)		
A			0.016			0.008		
B			0.011			0.006		
A X B			0.022			0.011		
C			0.016			0.008		
A X C			0.031			0.016		
B X C			0.022			0.011		
A X B X C			0.044			0.022		

Treatment details

T₁ : Wheat flour

T₂ : Wheat flour 60g + Unripe Banana flour 50g+ Xanthan gum 2g

The amount of water absorbed in macaroni is directly influenced by the gluten protein. When the temperature reaches the gelatinization point, the gluten protein in the noodles denatures and creates a link, blocking water penetration. (Kovacs et al., 2004). Due to their high dietary fibre and amylose contents, pasta products prepared with unripe banana flour have a higher water absorption capacity than pasta made with whole wheat flour (Adebowale et al., 2012).

Mabogo *et al.* (2021) reported that the largest water absorption capacity and swelling capacity were observed in banana flour (2.85 per cent and 1.14 per cent) compared to control (1.25 per cent and 1.88 per cent) because of the loose amylopectin and amylose connection in the natural starch association on control flour. The production of dry noodles using unripe banana flour was investigated by Anggraeni *et al.* (2018). The physiochemical features investigation found that the low protein and high starch content of the noodles with 0, 10, and

30% unripe banana flour increased the water absorption by 157, 169, and 180 percent respectively.

Changes in the rehydration ratio of macaroni during storage:

Table 4 displays Changes in the rehydration ratio of macaroni during storage. The longest period of time needed for macaroni to rehydrate satisfactorily among the treatments was 12.30 minutes. The macaroni samples packed in P₁ and P₂ had a rehydration ratio of 1.82 to 2.01 while the control (T₁) varied from 1.82 to 2.07. After 90 days of storage, the rehydration ratio of T₂ was varied from 1.95 to 2.19 and 2.12 for the samples packed in P₁ and P₂. The rehydration ratio of every sample packed in both packing materials progressively increased. However, the rehydration ratio of the macaroni packed in P₂ was low. Iyn (2013) reported that millet-supplemented pasta products have less gluten protein content because they have a greater rehydration ratio than control pasta. After being stored, the soy meal maker increased the macaroni's rehydration ratio from 1.76 to 1.94 (Kavitha, 2006).

Table.4. Changes in the rehydration ratio of macaroni during storage

Storage days	T ₁		T ₂		T ₃		T ₄	
	P ₁	P ₂						
Initial	1.82	1.82	1.95	1.95	1.90	1.90	1.95	1.95
30	1.89	1.84	2.02	1.97	1.97	1.95	2.01	1.99
60	1.97	1.93	2.10	2.06	2.05	1.99	2.10	2.06
90	2.07	2.01	2.19	2.12	2.12	2.06	2.18	2.11
Factors			C.D.			SE(d)		
A			0.011			0.006		
B			0.008			0.004		
A X B			0.016			0.008		
C			0.011			0.006		
A X C			N/A			0.011		
B X C			0.016			0.008		
A X B X C			N/A			0.016		

Treatment details

T₁ : Wheat flour

T₂ : Wheat flour 60g + Unripe Banana flour 50g+ Xanthan gum 2g

Changes in the Resistant Starch (RS) content of macaroni during storage:

Table 5 shows Changes in the Resistant Starch (RS) content of macaroni during storage. On the first day of storage, it was observed that the initial resistant starch contents of the control (T₁) and unripe banana flour incorporated macaroni (T₂) were 2.29 and 22.02 per cent. The resistant starch content of the unripe banana flour incorporated macaroni percent (T₂) and the control (T₁) had increased to 2.43 to 2.41 and 22.38 and 22.36 percent respectively, packed in HDPE and MPP at the end of the storage period. The resistant starch level of the unripe banana flour-supplemented macaroni was higher than that of the macaroni made with whole wheat flour, according to the data displayed in the tables.

Table.5. Changes in the Resistant Starch (g/100g) content of macaroni during storage

Storage days	T ₁		T ₂		T ₃		T ₄	
	P ₁	P ₂						
Initial	2.29	2.29	22.02	22.02	22.04	22.04	22.01	22.01
30	2.33	2.30	22.37	22.35	22.40	22.37	22.37	22.34
60	2.38	2.36	22.43	22.41	22.45	22.43	22.43	22.41
90	2.43	2.41	22.48	22.46	22.48	22.45	22.47	22.45
Factors			C.D.			SE(d)		
A			0.007			0.003		
B			0.005			0.002		
A X B			N/A			0.005		
C			0.007			0.003		
A X C			0.013			0.007		
B X C			0.009			0.005		
A X B X C			0.019			0.009		

Treatment details

T₁ : Wheat flour

T₂ : Wheat flour 60g + Unripe Banana flour 50g+ Xanthan gum 2g

The developed macaroni products' ideal resistant starch concentration varied from 2.29 to 22.38g/100g. Dhital *et al.* (2010) reported that the molecular retrogradation of gelatinized and fragmented amylose during storage was the cause of the rise in resistant starch.

A study on the formation of dry fresh and dry noodles from unripe banana flour incorporated at the levels of 10, 20, 30, and 40% found that raising the proportion of banana flour increased the amount of resistant starch in the noodles. At this degree of addition, the resistant starch concentration was 9.54, 13.37, 18.03, and 23.31 per cent, however, 5.565 per cent of resistant starch was found in the control sample (Tangthanantorn et al., 2021). Salted noodles made with 20% unripe banana flour contained 10.92% resistant starch, compared to 3.25% in the control sample (Li et al., 2022).

CONCLUSION

The cooking quality assessment of banana flour incorporated macaroni during storage revealed that the best cooking times for macaroni was 8.30 to 6.67 minutes, gruel loss was 3.62 to 5.69 per cent, water absorption was 182.40 to 201.80 ml, and the rehydration ratio was 1.82 to 2.19. The optimum resistant starch content was 2.29 per cent. The results of cooking property factors indicated that macaroni kept in MPP performed better in all quality characteristics. The results of the trial showed that macaroni prepared with unripe banana flour performed better than the macaroni prepared with wheat flour.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

Conceptualization of research (SR, BM, KS); Contribution of materials (BM, SR, KS, PR, RK); Analysis of data and Interpretation (BM, SR, PR); Preparation of Manuscript ((BM, SR, KS, PR, RK).

DECLARATION

All authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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